

PROSPECTS AND BARRIERS FOR DEVELOPMENT TOURISM IN RURAL AREAS WARMIA AND MAZURY

Perspektywy i bariery rozwoju turystyki na obszarach wiejskich Warmii i Mazur

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Summary

Warmia and Mazury have large European scale tourism and natural values. Attraction is the landscape of these areas, forests, lakes, clean natural environment, and numerous monuments of architecture and culture. The region is particularly well suited to the development of recreational functions, tourism, rural tourism and qualified - sailing, Horsemanship, hiking or cycling.

The development of tourism in the world, that tourism is becoming one of the most important sectors of the economy for many countries. The authorities of the voivodship involve high hopes the development of tourism, seeing it as an opportunity for economic growth in the region. Tourism is a big area, but still unused opportunities of development for the voivodship. A major difficulty is the poor accessibility of the region, but also inadequate offer tourist and recreational facilities.

The development of tourism in rural areas can significantly contribute to the creation of new jobs, allowing the region's economic development and meet the vital needs of its residents. In the current situation of tourism that brings an additional source of income for the population engaged in agriculture, but it certainly could become an alternative source of income for the ineffectiveness of many agricultural activities, especially small farms. Agrotourism is also the opportunity to develop other activities. Its development is mainly conditioned by the investment opportunities and promote the values of recreation in rural areas.

1. Introduction

Tourism in rural areas is the area of the region to create branded products, whose quality depends critically on conditions resulting from his natural predispositions. The trips to the countryside decide to seek alternatives to the conditions of everyday life. Therefore a priority in the development of rural tourism in Warmia and Mazury is to preserve the environment in the state of the least transformed. Stimulator to accelerate the development of tourism in the country is any investment that contributes to the improvement of rivers and lakes, as well as all investments relating to the maintenance of cleanliness and good sanitary conditions in the region. The unique natural and landscape and low population density, agricultural character of the province, forest cover and a large number of bodies permits the development of different forms of tourism and recreation. An additional factor influencing the attractiveness of the residence is a rich cultural heritage.

The strategy for socio-economic development of the Warmia and Mazury in rural tourism is a very important position. Particular attention is paid to the growth potential of tourism and the wider promotion of the province and shares its tourist offer. Due to the fact that tourism is one of the main areas of sustainable development in Warmia and Mazury, and has significant opportunities for development, has been treated in the Regional Operational Programme of Warmia and Mazury in a special way, acting in a separate priority axis.

2. The importance of tourism in rural development

Tourism is now one of the fastest growing industries in the world. In 1999, the tourism industry generated 11% of world gross national product, providing employment to 200 million people, which accounted for 8% of all employees. Forecasts of global tourism development, developed in 2010, also provides for the creation of 5.5 million new jobs annually (World Travel & Tourism Council 1999). Poland is still in a period of intense change. I still do not make full use of our vast tourism potential and we are not fully competitive on the European market. Everything depends on the development of the national product, which must meet the quality requirements of international markets.

Such a product will attract tourists to the Polish and reduce the mass migrations of Polish tourists abroad. Specificity of the Polish agriculture as a chapter of the national economy lies in the fact that it brings together more than a quarter of the national labor force, and its share in the production of gross domestic product does not exceed 10%. Therefore, income, and hence the standard of living of the rural population is much lower than the urban population. The bad, the income of rural families is the cause of social conflict and political and reduces the possibility of funding education for young people, causing a deep-rooted civilizational backwardness. Modernisation and restructuring of agriculture in this era of market economy, structural change will involve not only the agricultural production, but also rural areas in general. The most serious task to be faced is the state policy towards agriculture and rural areas, is to stop the decline in incomes of rural families and setting up mechanisms pro-profit among others. through the creation of new jobs.

One of the courses of action in this regard is the development of tourism. It combines the ability to shape the conditions for sustainable rural development with environmental conservation and preservation of rural heritage. Activities agrotourism should therefore:

1. to protect and enrich the natural and landscape values of rural areas,
2. strive to preserve the productive potential, especially land resources suitable for agricultural use,
3. create new jobs, and thus prevent excessive migration of population from rural to urban areas.

Both eulogised and reviled as a development option, rural tourism is increasingly viewed as a panacea, increasing the economic viability of marginalised areas, stimulating social regeneration and improving the living conditions of rural communities. Less developed countries, afflicted by debilitating rural poverty, have considerable potential in attracting tourists in search of new, authentic experiences in areas of unexploited natural and cultural riches.

Evolving tourist trends have, over the last decade, led to a shift from standardised mass tourism to more individualistic patterns, in which greater flexibility and a more meaningful experience have gained prominence (Poon, 1989, Hummelbrunner & Miglbauer, 1994, Gilbert, 1989, Pigram, 1993). It has been argued that rural tourists have varied motivations, which might include ecological uniqueness, special adventure opportunities, cultural attractions, or the peace and quiet of the countryside (Sharpley & Sharpley, 1997, Page & Getz, 1997). Greffe suggests that this presents a unique opportunity for rural operators to manage in terms of 'economies of scope' by establishing networks of different service providers, organised in such a way as to maximise opportunity and offer a diverse range of activities. For suppliers of rural tourism this emphasises the significance of the development of product, which attracts, satisfies and retains the market (Greffe, 1994, Hummelbrunner & Miglbauer, 1994). Clustering of activities and attractions, the erection of user-friendly signage, the establishment of easily accessible information offices, and the development of rural tourism routes, which stimulate entrepreneurial opportunity, the development of ancillary services and provide a diverse range of optional activities, has become decisive in securing business in less developed rural areas (Greffe, 1994, Chassagne, 1991, Gunn, 1979, Fagence, 1991, Lew, 1991, Miossec, 1977, Long, Perdue, & Allen, 1990, Getz & Page, 1997). Effort is focused on maximising individual spend, and providing products and experiences that act as an incentive to tourists to stay longer and return on repeat visits (Kinsley, 2000).

In many countries, rural tourism has enjoyed substantial encouragement, support and, in some cases, direct financial assistance from both the public and private sectors (Fleischer, Pizam, 1997). According to Hall and Jenkins (1998), such intervention and support is unsurprising. Over the last three decades, many rural economies have suffered a severe downturn, with falling employment and income levels in traditional agrarian industries contributing to a vicious circle of economic decline and socio-economic problems. In particular, per capita rural incomes have fallen well below national averages, whilst the loss of public services, high unemployment levels and the consequential out-migration of younger, better educated members of rural communities have collectively endangered the fabric and structure of rural areas (OECD, 1993). As a result, not only has tourism been embraced as a potential means of reversing this decline but also, given the intimate relationship between the socio-economic health of rural areas in general and the prosperity of the farming community in particular, it has become an integral element of rural development policy.

This increasing dependence on and support for rural tourism is based upon a number of perceived benefits it potentially provides to rural areas. Generally, rural tourism is seen as a valuable and growing sector of the overall tourism market, representing a significant source of income to rural economies (Hummelbrunner, Miglbauer, 1994). For example, it has been estimated that rural tourism in England generates about 9 billion pounds annually (Countryside Commission, 1995). More specifically, the development of rural tourism offers potential solutions to many of the problems facing rural areas (ETB, 1988; Thibal, 1988; Kieselbach, Long, 1990; Gannon, 1994; OECD, 1994). These may be summarised as:

- Economic growth, diversification and stabilisation through employment creation in both new (tourism related) and existing businesses, trades and crafts; opportunities for income growth through pluriactivity (Fuller, 1990); the creation of new markets for agricultural products; and, a broadening of a region's economic base.
- Socio-cultural development, including the re-population of rural areas; the maintenance and improvement of public services; the revitalisation of local crafts, customs and cultural identities; and, increased opportunities for social contact and exchange.
- Protection and improvement of both the natural and built environment and infrastructure.

The extent to which these benefits are realised remains the subject of debate. Certainly, there is evidence to support the claim that, as a vehicle of economic growth and diversification, tourism can make an important contribution to rural incomes both at the level of the individual farmer and more widely in the local economy (ETB, 1991). Equally,

there is little doubt that tourism is an important source of employment, particularly in traditionally popular rural destinations, and can play a fundamental role in the social and environmental development of rural areas.

At the same time, however, the notion that tourism represents a panacea to the problems facing rural areas, that it is a 'magic wand that will speed up economic progress' (Hoggart et al., 1995), must be treated with some caution. That is, the extent to which tourism contributes effectively to rural development and diversification, hence the extent to which it is deserving of government support and finance, is questioned in many quarters (Hall, Jenkins, 1998). In general, of course, the development of rural tourism – as with most other forms of tourism – may have undesirable economic, social and environmental consequences for local communities (Gannon, 1994). However, studies have also shown that a number of factors militate against the achievement of rural economic diversification and growth through tourism.

In particular, it has been found that tourism contributes relatively little extra to farm incomes, with the returns from investing in tourism – primarily in accommodation facilities – rarely meeting expectations (Hjalager, 1996; Opperman, 1996). To an extent, this can be explained by the fact that rural tourism enterprises tend to be small scale and supply a highly seasonal market (Fleischer, Pizam, 1997), although it is indicative of a number of challenges facing the successful diversification into tourism. These include:

1. Not all rural areas are equally attractive to rural tourists and simply providing accommodation facilities does not guarantee demand. The total product package must be sufficient to attract and keep tourists, offering suitable opportunities for spending (Gannon, 1994).
2. Developing and organising rural tourism may require a significant investment either beyond the means of the business owner or greater than justified by potential returns. In such cases, government subsidies may be required to maintain the social benefits of diversification into tourism (Fleischer, Felenstein, 2000).
3. Local communities and businesses may find it difficult to adapt to a service role. For example, Hajalager (1996) observes that European farmers found it difficult to combine the 'commodification of agricultural traditions' through tourism with the industry of agriculture. In other words, agricultural values and guest-service values are frequently incompatible (Fleischer, Pizam, 1997).
4. The quality of products and services must match tourists demands and expectations. In the Bran region in central Romania, for example, the success of rural tourism was hampered by a failure to meet the needs of overseas visitors (Roberts, 1996).
5. Individual rural tourism enterprises normally possess neither the skills nor the resources for effective marketing, a prerequisite to success (Embacher, 1994). In many regions or countries, marketing and advertising support is available, although it has been found that rural communities may be suspicious or even resentful of 'outside' assistance.

These challenges are not, of course, all evident in every situation. However, they do suggest that tourism is not necessarily a solution to the problems facing rural areas. That is, tourism may not always represent the most suitable development path, whilst the costs and other difficulties summarised above may limit the potential economic returns.

The potential of tourism routes has long been realised in developed countries. In 1964 a Council of Europe working group mooted the idea of a series of European Cultural Routes, with the prime objectives of raising awareness of European culture through travel, setting up networks for cultural tourism, and utilising European cultural heritage as a means of stimulating social, economic and cultural development, thus improving the quality of life of local people. The idea however only came to fruition in 1980 with the establishment of the Santiago de Compostela Pilgrim Ways. The term Cultural Tourism Route was defined as 'a route crossing one or two more countries or regions, organised around themes whose historical, artistic or social interest is patently European...the route must be based on a number of highlights, with places particularly rich in historical associations'. Twenty years later the project is described as 'an instrument for understanding the European values arising from the complex cultures and societies that have formed Europe'. The program, with over 2000 partners, is based on multilateral co-operation involving a chain of projects and information sharing networks, monitored and coordinated by the European Institute of Cultural Routes ([Council of Europe, 2002](#)).

In the United States heritage trails have been shown to provide the impetus for the development of a range of attractions and facilities along their routes ([Hill and Gibbons, 1994](#)). Hill and Gibbons point out that Western heritage trails, in particular, have served as a catalyst for the stimulation of theatrical productions, wagon trains, horseback trails and diverse other attractions and activities relished by tourists. Hill argues that since tourists are dispersed along the length of the trail, management of carrying capacity is facilitated, negative environmental impacts reduced, and economic benefits more evenly distributed ([Hill and Gibbons, 1994](#)). The initiation of co-operation and partnership between different local areas, regions, states and, as the cross-border rural tourism stimulated by the opening of the border between Finland and Russian Karelia would indicate, occasionally countries, is perceived as an additional benefit of such development ([Hill and Gibbons, 1994](#), [Selin and Friman, 2002](#)).

The 2000–2002 Cultural Tourism Incentive Programme "The Queensland Heritage Trails Network" has been initiated with the objective to 'revitalise rural and regional Queensland economies through the creation of jobs and a sustainable tourism infrastructure'. The project, which functions in partnership with local government, aims at developing a network of thirty-two major projects, developed around themes for particular local areas or regions, and promoting linkages which stimulate and encourage tourists to travel through the state, venturing away from major

attractions and enjoying new experiences offered by the lesser-known surrounding areas ([Queensland Heritage Trails Network, 2000](#)). The definition of heritage is broad-based and includes 'historical, environmental and traditional values, as well as how the spirit of Queenslanders shows itself through an empathy with the land, through a sense of community continuity and through stories of individual achievement'.

3. Social, economic and environmental importance of tourism.

Any messages available to modern science, suggest a genetic relationship of man with nature, and prove conclusively the phased, natural development. This means that a person at all stages of their anthropogenesis always been harmoniously connected with nature and maintain its solid, natural touch.

Man usurping the autonomy of modern civilization and the continuous relaxation of close ties with the natural environment, began to rapidly produce irreparable losses and catastrophic consequences. For all the "convenience", with which he began to take full advantage of computerized technical and his world, he had to pay the bill in a different, previously unknown diseases, generally regarded by modern medicine for so-called diseases of civilization.

It is the rapid progress of technology and various related conditions, and above all the noise, the constant rush, excess stress, reducing the time to relax and sometimes even lack of sleep, etc. cause adverse human body burden. The above-mentioned negative effects on the human individual, it is primarily the nervous system overload, which leads to an imbalance in the body, and mainly in the sphere of mental disorders.

Method to eliminate the above negative effects on the rapid pace of development of civilization is to find methods and rapid regeneration of the human body. Nothing soothes the nerves and dismisses fatigue as a quiet hum of the forest, singing birds, the splash of running water, which is in contact with the natural environment, away from the hustle and bustle and noise, in contact with plants and animals. Such a psychological comfort can provide recreation in the countryside.

4. The economic importance of tourism

The activities of tourist farm can bring many benefits, both for the working farm as well as for the whole community and rural development in the regions and municipalities.

Activation of entrepreneurship in rural areas.

The greatest activity in this respect are manifested in people aged 40 years and with at least secondary education. The survey shows that women hold a higher level of education than men, while conditions of rural tradition obliges them to care for family, home and household. They are the engine of development of tourism.

Additional income to the farm (accommodation, meals, sales of agricultural products).

The farm source of income may be renting accommodation, meals for guests, and the sale of agricultural products from own farm directly to tourists or those persons engaged in catering. Prices of these products are often higher than wholesale, especially if you are certified healthy food. **Development of crafts and folk art.**

Tourists who take leave are less inclined to save than those in everyday life. Sociological and psychological studies confirm the more "wasteful" of people at that time. Thus opening up new opportunities for gifts industry.

Progress in breeding, farming and gardening.

Very popular for tourists are products from own farm and especially organically produced. However, not all plants will give an appropriate yield in organic farming and integrated. In animal production with the development of rural tourism services has increased interest in breeding horses for recreational purposes. A true renaissance has been made in breeding goats and small furry animals. Particular progress is noticeable in horticultural production, as many vegetables and fruits are eaten raw, and people recognize their taste and appearance.

Additional jobs.

Service for guests, caring for a neat workarround and order, preparing meals, etc.. classes are very labor intensive. Especially since the idea of tourism is courteous and comprehensive care for tourists. At their request, the host should always be time for them, and pronouncing with an excess of classes at the farm is out of place. Therefore, the period of increased influx of tourists in a project involving the whole family, and often there is the need to hire additional people, at least seasonally. Additional jobs are also created on the occasion of the appointment of the local tourist information offices, extra amenities, etc. The implementation of a comprehensive rural development strategy will force investment in rural and regional level (the development of technical infrastructure), which also creates new employment opportunities.

Diversification of the economy.

Agrotourism can result in a comprehensive economic recovery, not only because of the increasing demand for healthy food, but equally stimulate the growth of all kinds of services (shops, snack-bar, hairdressing, crafts, artwork), directed at the security needs of tourists.

Improving the utilization rates of living space and economic activity.

Typically, each family has a rural residential house with an area larger than the average flat in the block. Then there are no small warehouse and economic and attics are not used properly. Adaptation of these areas for tourism improves the utilization rate of the surface.

Supporting local services and processing.

The development of tourism creates even need to expand its activities in many areas, not only at the individual

household, but the entire village or community. Clearest reflection of this is in a higher demand for different products, not just food, which means a significant boost trade. More tourists are increasing demand for necessities, cleaning supplies, newspapers, etc. The broad scope of activity opens before the small agricultural processing plants - local dairies, bakeries, butchers and small catering establishments - fry fish, bakeries, etc. Others are plant hairdressing, massage services, undertaking home repair, car repair shop, a pharmacy.

Investments - the development of infrastructure. Impossible is development of tourism in rural areas without adequate technical support. On a scale of one household are needed renovated guestrooms with free access to the bathroom (brought water and sanitation). This requirement also applies to camping. The development of this theme also attracts investment in the whole village or community. The most important is the construction of roads, water and gas pipelines and treatment plants.

5. Barriers to agrotourism activity

Economic barrier at the start.

Starting agrotourism activity requires at the start of high volume, mainly on the adaptation of premises or facilities, such as water supply, sewerage.

Exclusion of land from production for other purposes.

Even on a scale of one farm agrotourism activities require "sacrifices" in the form of land. Organization campsite, pitches for team games and other recreational areas at the expense of agricultural land, acreage, and so are still shrinking. Similarly, development of technical infrastructure, expanding the network of service points will often irrevocable transformation of agricultural land in others. Mass reduction of agricultural land area, especially high-class valuation in favor of other activities is not acceptable even in the current socio-economic conditions.

Changing the structure of land ownership.

The development of agrotourism activity causes the region's economic recovery, which is naturally a positive phenomenon. However, any investment takes place first at the expense of agricultural land, and often it is also necessary for the redemption of land ownership. This raises the trend of decreasing average farm area, excessive fragmentation of land, which is contrary to the concept of prospective development of agriculture in Poland, assuming at least two-fold increase in surface area of the average household.

Additional infrastructure and services.

Although technical progress in rural areas is the most mentioned, it can be presumed that the allocation for tourism development could well be used for agriculture alone, even in the promotion of biological development, purchase of machinery, tools, etc. The main objective of farmers is still food production, while in some regions most of the forces and resources is subordinated to tourism.

The increase in the holiday settlement.

Massive sell off plots for construction of recreation may be the cause of the loss of agricultural character and attractive natural landscapes of some regions. In addition to progressing in such cases, fragmentation of land, uncontrolled chalets area poses a danger label.

Temporary increase in population density.

The massive influx of tourists into the area, regardless of whether they will be guests of the farmers or owners of a cottage in the area, can contribute to the loss of values that made this attractive holiday village. The promotion of agro-tourism one of the most important points is to offer the holiday in peace and quiet, the fresh air, unpolluted environment.

The increase in prices of building land.

Landscape and natural attractiveness of the city, enriched also open to the public infrastructure and offer a comprehensive recreation, can inflate the prices offered land to the extent that they become accessible to the few wealthy citizens, and the farmer will not be able to buy back from his neighbor's land unnecessary.

The outflow of labor to tourism (summer season).

Possibility of finding employment, even seasonally, it is important, particularly in the area with a high degree of unemployment. But we must remember that during the biggest influx of tourists, we also have to deal with a large accumulation of work in agriculture. Quite often it is difficult to reconcile the complete service guests with timely implementation of the necessary field work. In these farms, each pair of hands is important, and the children and young people in an even greater extent than before is the involvement of all ancillary, remaining without any chance for a summer holiday. Excess of classes during the summer makes it often chooses to be a priority. If the holding of a major source of income is income from tourism, farming limping will suffer even more. Moreover, in most cases, the movement agrotourism in Poland is closely linked only to the period of the summer. Thus, tourism will not be a long time remedy for the prevailing unemployment and can not solve all the problems of agriculture.

Traffic overload (low security).

The vast majority of tourists, even those who prefer a healthy and active recreation, the place manages to leave the car. Among the guests will find a population which assume a group of tourists visiting the near and far as using the car. Besides the increase in tourists in the city makes it necessary to transport for larger quantities of goods. These factors are causing a significant increase in traffic on the roads. The average village has long since ceased to be a safe route through the development of the automobile, and now have become an attractive tourist village in this regard as

hazardous as the city.

The increase in expenditures on maintenance of roads and railways.

Accommodation provider can not count on an excess of guests and their re-appointment, if the way to the holding of a car stuck in mud or damaged. The access road directly to the farm does not need to be covered with asphalt, but must allow safe access at any time of year, regardless of weather conditions. Thus, at both the village and the region's road-building seems to be paramount in terms of convenience of guests and for safety reasons. In addition, increased traffic, and faster depreciation of roads and the need for frequent repairs, (Mlynarczyk).

6. Prospects for development of rural tourism in the region of Warmia and Mazury

Strong motivations of people looking for new ideas for additional sources of income, proximity to natural attractions, the possibility of their links with other departments of tourism in the region - is a leading characteristics of rural tourism in the Warmia - Mazury. Rural accommodation is a close partner of active tourism, business and transit purposes. The proposed products of rural tourism: accommodation, group and individual housing units, guest houses, regional products or gifts are a vital part of tourism in the region.

Opportunities for tourism development in rural areas of Warmia and Mazury may be found at:

- organic food production and traditional,
- possible use of equipment and livestock for the purposes of recreation and rehabilitation care,
- possible adoption of the new professional roles (guides, carriers, custodians disabled children),
- adaptation for tourism architecturally interesting areas of farm and craft: forges, mills, windmills, etc.
- cultivating at the level of educational professions and skills associated with traditional agriculture and rural life: weaving, metalwork, embroidery, sculpture, glass painting, etc.
- creating an organization of all regional associations,
- learning opportunities at the University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, specializing in tourism.

Fot. 1. Kitchen on agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 2. Kitchen on agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 3. Room on agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

An extremely important assets in the development of rural tourism and agrotourism in the Warmia and Mazury are enormous opportunities and favorable conditions for producing exceptional and unique traditional foods associated

with a rich and complex history of the region. Taking up new activities of a manufacturing and marketing creates new sources of off-farm income. In many cases, such actions are carried out by outsiders, often young residents of large cities, the countryside who discover new resources and extensive business opportunities. New challenges and needs that arise in recent years, are not only related to the abandonment of farming activities, but also are focused on exploration and making organic food production methods, cultivation of new plant species, alternative farming or food processing. Taking advantage of the growing demand for tourism-related recreation in the countryside, traditional services and products, persons engaged in the business agrotourism increasingly indicate in their bids to return to old habits, and forgotten legacy of culinary tastes. To meet the needs of tourists offer culinary evenings, ask the guests to the common baking bread, making cheese, fruit and vegetable and fruit liqueurs, organize workshops, pottery, embroidery and wickerwork. Based on the on the old, forgotten rules and recipes, while using products from their own or neighboring farms. On the other hand, buyers looking for a product consisting of a diverse tourism proposals for rural residents, among which is primarily a good, homemade meals and the opportunity to purchase traditional products. Such products must be authentically related to the tradition of the place or region, derived from local raw materials by using the original methods of production. Only then will they emphasized the specificity of the region and will become his trademark.

The offer of rural tourism and rural tourism board is significant. In order to reduce the cost of food services provided to guests it is recommended that raw food allowance from their own plantations or farms, which also allows on-site disposal of products at the farm, reducing the time associated with shopping, and above all improves the quality of food and increases the attractiveness of the farm. Positive identification of market needs and consumer preferences and the possibility of direct sales of traditional products allow you to take these production lines, for which there is demand, too, eg ecological way of cultivation, traditional methods of food processing. Products and enrich the traditional dishes of both dining and tourist farms, as well as the local gastronomy.

Fot. 4. Agrotourism farm recommended by the Polish Federation of Rural Tourism

Source: author collections

The growing interest in farms agrotourist offer is the best testimony to the need for tourist attractions of the region of Warmia and Mazury, with the increasing demand for traditional products. However, direct sales of these products is the most cost-effective form, where value added is a labor and culinary heritage. Linking attractiveness of Warmia and Mazury with genuine products creates new opportunities for the promotion of the region.

Among the benefits of the region to manufacture traditional products include:

new image of the region - more attractive to tourists,
job creation,
multi-skilling, which marks the emergence of professions other than farmers, which requires the preparation of the product on the market,
diversification of income for the inhabitants of the region,
sustaining farms, which are likely to develop only in connection with the manufacture of such products,
the use of regional resources accompanying a product: forests, handicrafts, folk art,
mobilization of women,
supporting the development of local initiatives to create more sources of income, extra-curricular activities,
gain further experience in the field of entrepreneurship and regional development - "taking matters into their own hands".

Organization development initiatives around regional product is the best way to emphasize the identity of the area, develop cooperation with neighboring areas, using common features and common roots, the selfeducation local communities. The symbol of the region is identified with its regional product (Duczowska-Malysz, 2006).

Fot. 5. Information about the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 6. Information about the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

The strategy of tourism development in Warmia and Mazury proposes the following actions:

- construction of facilities for tourism-oriented rural health prevention - rural sanatoriums, facilities using climatic advantages, the possibility of long-term rehabilitation in peace and quiet,
- create holiday packages on Saturdays and Sundays as a proposal for the urban population of the neighboring provinces,
- activation of the lagoon area,
- use the potential of closing rural schools and creating in them the "white and green schools" for children from the cities,
- promote regional cuisine in farm tourism,
- create a base for people with disabilities as well as the base for the elderly,
- creation of workplaces offer for seeking accommodation and conference rooms, training and motivational meetings and integration, the therapeutic classes and workshops,
- create an effective system of information on rural tourism offer, well linked with the regional tourist information system,
- continuing the process of categorization of rural accommodation,
- placement in strategic locations water parks,
- concern for the preservation of indigenous local traditions and cultural identities of immigrant residents in creating a tourism product in rural areas (Strategy, 2001).

Fot. 7. Information about the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 8. Animals on the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

To the deliberate actions of local authorities in tourism development and promotion of regional product identifies a number of projects, initiatives and competitions that take place in the region of Warmia and Mazury.

One of the actions in this regard is the competition "Our Culinary Heritage", whose idea is to encourage the rural population, especially those with handicaps, to seek alternative sources of income, raising awareness of rural residents about the opportunities to develop food production, based on local raw material and using conventional technologies.

"Tastes of Warmia and Mazury Vistula on the tables of Europe" is a competition organized by the Local Government Warmia and Mazury and Warmia and Mazury Chamber of Agriculture, which is part of the implementation of Warmia and Mazury Quality Promotion Program, the Program "Improving the quality of food service and hospitality for the region Mazur in 2004-2013, "contained in the Strategy for Socio-Economic Development of Warmia and Mazury. The competition aims to gather unique recipes from rural areas to promote the region and only one of its kinds of dishes that are specific to the culinary heritage of our region. The participants of the competition are rural inhabitants of Warmia, Mazury and parts Powisle adherent to the Warmia and Mazury. Reported products are judged in two categories: products associated with natives of Warmia, Mazury and Powisle and products associated with the people who came to the area of Warmia, Mazury Vistula region after 1945.

Culinary Heritage Warmia Masuria Powisle is part of the European Network of Regional Culinary Heritage, whose members in each region are selected farmhouses, producers, food processing plants and restaurants, emphasizing its links with the region. Manufacturers must meet the criteria for products and dishes found in foods of local origin (Operation ... 2005). The idea of a regional product determines its origins, and assumes that from farm to table should be linked with the region. Appropriate logo or certification is the best passport to regional food as well as for tourist farms belonging to the network. State enterprises using the mark Network Culinary Heritage Warmia Masuria Powisle promote themselves, the region of Warmia, Mazury and Vistula and the whole of the European Network of Regional Culinary Heritage.

Fot. 9. Regional and traditional products from the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 10. Regional and traditional products from the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

All of the above-described action is to identify tourist farms and the products they produce.

7. Indicators figures for households providing tourist services in rural areas

According to estimates, conducted by field advisors Center of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn Agricultural Advisory Service, the area of the voivodship there are about 2 500 - 3 000 households, providing tourist services in rural areas. These households can be divided into:

farmhouses – 960,

rural tourism facilities – 1500, organic farms – 80.

The Warmia and Mazury operates 2,540 households, of which only 888 are registered in the municipal records of other providers of tourist accommodation facilities. Within a year of rest in the country uses about 143,000 people, most of whom are choosing 7 - day stay. Farms offer an average of 8 - 9 beds. The average price of accommodation and meals are formed in the field: 34 polish zloty per night / overnight stays (from 30 to 60 polish zloty), 35 polish zloty for full board per person (from 22 to 45 polish zloty). Accommodation agritourism farms is used on average 30 - 40 days a year. Only objects with long-serving rent rooms for 60 - 70 days a year. The biggest use of accommodation falls in the summer months (July and August) - from 40% to 60% in the remaining months (May, June, September and January) ranges from 10.3% - 15.7% (Information, 2008).

Fot. 11. View of the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 12. View of the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

Fot. 13. View of the agrotourism farm

Source: author collections

In European countries with longstanding traditions of rural tourism, the use of accommodation is at a level of 100 days a year and the average farm not for at least 30% of total revenue. Given the significant increase in investments in modernization and improvement of quality accommodation tourist accommodation and services, so little use of accommodation in the Warmia and Mazury does not guarantee the viability of tourism services.

8. Barriers to the development of rural tourism in the region of Warmia and Mazury

Agrotourism and rural tourism occupy a very important place in rural development warmińsko-mazurskie. Through boom and generate demand for services related to recreation in the countryside, created opportunities for other activities, is forced to take up and the need to expand trade, catering, transport and recreational sports. These activities contribute to the creation of new jobs and non-agricultural sources of income, which undoubtedly improves the living conditions in rural areas. Tourism in rural areas is a chance for economic recovery of the Warmia and Mazury.

In addition to a number of reasons to the development of rural tourism in the Warmia and Mazury, there are a number of barriers to development resulting from general economic situation in the region. Here are some of them.

- Another factor hindering the development of the state of rural infrastructure. Network is insufficient and the quality of roads, water supply and sanitation, lack of bicycle paths, recreation centers, sports and culture, difficult access to banks, post offices and health care providers. An important barrier for tourists is also low accessibility of the region.
- Significant reduction in tourism development in rural areas is low availability of farm owners to finance. To benefit from EU funds is limited not only to complex procedures and the need to invest in the initial phase of their own resources, but also because of the prohibitive rules on access to these funds.
- A significant obstacle in the conduct of tourism activities in rural areas is lack of knowledge of foreign languages, making it impossible to propose offers to foreigners.
- A frequent problem is lack of interest in local tourism. Service providers themselves have to take care of promotion and advertising of its facilities because the authorities are not interested in promoting this type of activity.
- A significant difficulty in the development of tourism in rural areas is the lack of mutual cooperation between the owners of the farm tourism. Interaction between service providers would contribute to creating a rich tourist offer.
- The development of tourism in rural areas requires the investment of adaptive, difficult financing for low income users and non-profit farms. Maintaining an adequate level of service quality agro-tourism and the shaping a positive image in the market for tourism is a system of categorization of rural accommodation. The Warmia and Mazury successful transition procedures for categorization can boast only 186 quarters. For most providers, categorization means raising the standard of accommodation and giving the whole object corresponding prestige. Obtaining the appropriate category agroturismo is associated with the following benefits:
 - the possibility of placing advertisements in catalogs issued by the Polish Federation of Rural Tourism "Hospitable Farms"
 - obtaining higher prices for services offered
 - greater interest from customers categorization object.

The accommodation does not conceal that the decision to carry out categorization was dictated by the duty to apply for financial assistance under the Sectoral Operational Programme. Most service points out that the categorization of the procedure should remain voluntary. The rationale for such a solution are not only high fees categorization, but also the inability to make their own decisions on what sort of run the farm. These concerns stem from the need to fulfill certain requirements, which resulted in often comes to the loss of originality and "homely-home" nature of the object. For many farmers categorization requirements are too stringent and difficult to achieve, and the cost of investments needed to improve the quality of service and obtain a category, or a higher grade is too high, or not economically justified.

Despite the undoubted benefits of tourism development in rural areas, a number of adversities limits its development. A worrying phenomenon is recorded by the statistics of declining revenues from tourism and the downward trend in arrivals of foreign tourists to our country. Reduced the rate of tourist accommodation, particularly accommodation tourism. Existing barriers translate into a state of development of tourism and leisure attraction in rural areas.

9. Summary

Warmia and Mazury have large European scale tourism and natural values. Attraction is the landscape of these areas, forests, lakes, clean natural environment, and numerous monuments of architecture and culture. The region is particularly well suited to the development of recreational functions, tourism, rural tourism and qualified - sailing, Horsemanship, hiking or cycling.

The development of tourism in the world, that tourism is becoming one of the most important sectors of the economy for many countries. The authorities of the voivodship involve high hopes the development of tourism, seeing it as an opportunity for economic growth in the region. Tourism is a big area, but still unused opportunities of development for the voivodship. A major difficulty is the poor accessibility of the region, but also inadequate offer tourist and recreational facilities.

The development of tourism in rural areas can significantly contribute to the creation of new jobs, allowing the region's economic development and meet the vital needs of its residents. In the current situation of tourism that brings an additional source of income for the population engaged in agriculture, but it certainly could become an alternative source of income for the ineffectiveness of many agricultural activities, especially small farms. Agrotourism is also the opportunity to develop other activities. Its development is mainly conditioned by the investment opportunities and promote the values of recreation in rural areas.

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